

TRAINING STUDENTS ON CREDIT TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF KAZAKHSTAN

FORMACIÓN DE ESTUDIANTES EN TECNOLOGÍA DEL CRÉDITO EN EDUCACIÓN DE KAZAJSTÁN

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Resumen

El objetivo de la investigación fue examinar el estado de los programas educativos nacionales de Kazajstán y compararlos con los programas educativos internacionales. La metodología de investigación fue un método de encuesta. Los resultados del estudio mostraron que el 55% de los estudiantes notaron que su nivel de motivación profesional era alto; el 45% de los estudiantes indicó que su nivel de motivación profesional era promedio o inferior al promedio. Sobre la base de los resultados obtenidos, se puede decir que existe una necesidad de motivación positiva para los estudiantes de pregrado. En consecuencia, se puede concluir que los programas nacionales han estado de acuerdo con los programas educativos internacionales.

Palabras clave: tecnología crediticia, sistema crediticio, sistema educativo, estudiante.

Abstract

The aim of the research was to examine the state of Kazakhstan's national educational programs and compare them with international educational programs. The research methodology was a survey method. The results of the study showed that 55% of the students noticed that their level of professional motivation was high; 45% of the students indicated that their level of professional motivation was average or below average. Based on the results obtained, it can be said that there is a need for positive motivation for undergraduate students. Consequently, it can be concluded that national programs have been in accordance with international educational programs.

Keywords: credit technology, credit system, educational system, student.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, in the context of globalization, Kazakhstan is one of the countries introducing a new education system - credit system, aimed at entering the world educational space. The search for ways to improve the quality of training specialists in universities, served as the basis for the development of innovative processes that embraced the introduction of new methods of teaching, the creation of new forms of the organization of the educational process, the use of new teaching aids, the richest possibilities of which are open thanks to scientific and technical progress (Abdrafikova, Akhmadullina, and Yarmakeev, 2015).

There is the possibility of choosing between options, which allows the teaching staff to choose and design pedagogical process for any model. Choice of teaching technology course is carried out by the teacher on the basis of the teacher's personal pedagogical convictions and makes up the teacher's individual style of pedagogical activity.

Credit technology is an educational technology that enhances level of self-education and creative mastering of knowledge on the basis of individualization, electivity of the educational trajectory within the strict regulation of the educational process and accounting for the amount of knowledge in the form of credits (Valiakhmetova, Akhmadullina, and Pimenova, 2017).

The credit system provides the organization of students on independent, active mastering the system of knowledge, abilities, skills, on accumulation of creative experience, on development of their educational cognitive activity, professional and cognitive needs, interests (Verbitsky, 2004; Pimenova, Abdrafikova, and Yarmakeev, 2017; Raven, 2002).

Independent work is an important component of the educational process. The quality of independent learning is determined by the following characteristics:

- feel the desire to work for mastering the subject;
- be able to rationally distribute their forces in lectures, seminars and in extra-curricular time;
- feel satisfaction from the received knowledge;
- feel responsible for the results of the training work.

However, in the context of increasing the role of independent work of students in the professional training of future specialists, changes in the place of independent work in the system of higher education, increased demands for the level of formation of subject competencies for independence as the quality of the personality of the future specialist, the organization of independent work of

students is presented insufficiently in the theory and practice of teaching (Raven, 2002).

According to the requirements of credit technology, each academic discipline is proposed for analyzing as a set of interrelated problems, arising from each other, which the student should learn from the guidance of the teacher mostly independently (Zymnyaya, 2003; Sergeev, 2004). Role of the teacher in this case is reduced to the formulation of the problem, substantiation of its relevance and practical significance and to the general management of the cognitive-creative activity of the student (Yakaeva, Salekhova, Kuperman, and Ksenia, 2017).

The use of this technology requires an immediate reduction in volume of group sessions of students with a teacher in the auditorium. Accordingly, the number of hours allocates for independent work of the student and his individual work with the teacher. The character of the control over the assimilation of knowledge of students also changes. Its main purpose is to evaluate the effectiveness of active search and cognitive activity of the student.

In this connection, a number of problems arise in the psychological and pedagogical plan, which can be classified as follows:

- adaptation of the student to the new system.
- adaptation of the teacher to the new system.

Concerning the advantage of a credit training system it can be said that it requires constant improvement of pedagogical skills, improvement of professional skills of the organizers of the educational process, exchange of best practices. This system requires the provision of an educational process with the methodology and practice of developing and optimizing use of modern information technologies, oriented toward the realization of the psychological and pedagogical goals of education and upbringing.

As the title of this research indicates “Training Students on Credit Technology in Educational System of Kazakhstan” the main objectives are: describing credit technology in educational system of Kazakhstan; establishing the significance of the system of higher education in the modern socially-oriented market economy; identifying the level of development of creative independence of students of higher education institutions in the conditions of credit technology and finally identifying the level of development of creative independence of students of higher education.

METHODOLOGY

Experimental work, with the purpose of identifying the level of development of creative independence of students of higher education institutions in the conditions of credit technology, was carried out on the basis of KorkytAta Kyzylorda State

University Kazakhstan. 136 Bachelor's degree students of 1, 2 courses, specializing in "Social Sciences, Economics and Business" and "Education", participated in the experimental work.

A set of methods and techniques for identifying the level of development of creative independence of students of higher education institutions in terms of credit technology has been selected and implemented in such areas of as "Social Sciences, Economics and Business" and "Education". Such methods are (Pimenova, Abdrafikova, Yarmakeev., 2017):

theoretical methods: analysis of philosophical, psychological, pedagogical, methodological, and linguistic literature; modeling; generalization of empirical material; synthesis of pedagogical experience of professors of higher education institutions;

empirical methods: observation – direct, indirect and included observation; analyzing of products of educational activity of students.

diagnostic methods: questioning, interviewing, test tasks.

experimental methods: establishing, forming and control stages, static – methods of mathematical statistics, the system and qualitative analysis of experimental data, their graphic interpretation. The following methodologies have been used in our research: "Technique for diagnostics of educational motivation of students" (Zeer and Symanyuk, 2005), "Technique of measurement of level of communicative competence of future expert" (Fahrutdinova, Fahrutdinov, and Konopatskaya, 2014).

Within the conducted research we have implemented the program for discipline "The English language", qualification: bachelor, form of analysis: full-time. Within implementation of this program, a set of tasks on independent work of students and independent work of students with the teacher were developed and approved with Bachelor's degree students of 1 - 2 courses.

At the establishing stage of the experimental work we studied the motives of the professional choice of bachelor students. For this purpose, we used the adapted technique by Zeer and Symanyuk (2005), as well as the methods that characterize the motives of the analysis, singled out by Valiakhmetova, Akhmadullina and Pimenova (2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main objective is the utilization of credit technology in educational system of Kazakhstan by using Zeer and Symanyuk (2005) technique. The purpose of using this technique was to recognize the formation of communicative, social, professional and educational-cognitive motives, as well as motivations for creative

self-realization, avoidance of failure and prestige.

Table No.1: Professional Motivation Levels of Students

Percentage	Frequency	
55	110	High professional motivation level
45	90	Low professional motivation level

Source: Authors (2018)

According to the research, 55% of students noted that the level of their professional motives was high; 45% of students noted that their level of formation of professional motives was at the level of average or below average.

Based on the results obtained, it is possible to mention the need to ensure positive motivation for Bachelor’s degree students to master their skills and skills of self-actualization in the field of professional activity in the process of their education.

We have also proposed a technique for measuring the level of communicative competence of a student, including thirty judgments. The methodology is based on the scaling method for a ten-point system. The use of this methodology allowed us to identify the following results.

Table No.2: The level of communicative competence of a student

Highest Level		Higher than Average		Average level		Mediocre level		Low level		
percentage	frequency	percentage	frequency	percentage	frequency	percentage	frequency	percentage	frequency	
15%	30	22%	44	38%	76	22%	44	3%	6	semantic load of the cognitive plan
15%	30	22%	44	38%	76	22%	44	3%	6	behavioral parameter
13%	26	24%	48	33%	66	26%	52	4%	8	teacher's ability

Source: Authors (2018)

The first judgments (1-10) contain the semantic load of the cognitive plan, the degree of the student's knowledge in the field of communication psychology: a low level was observed in 3% of students, a mediocre level in 22%, an average level of 38% of students, a level, higher than average, was noted in 22% of students, and the highest level is observed in 15%.

The second group of judgments (11-20) is aimed to determine the content of the behavioral parameter by means of which it becomes possible to characterize the features of the external behavior of the teacher in the course of communicating with students: a low level was observed in 3% of students, a mediocre level in 22%, an average level of 38% of students, a level, higher than average, was noted in 22% of students, and the highest level is observed in 15%.

The third group includes judgments (21-30), which reflect the teacher's ability to control his emotional state: a low level was found in 4% of students, a level, lower than average, of 26%, an average level of 33%, a high level in 24% of respondents and the highest level in 13%.

A comparative analysis of the results of the establishing and control stages of the experiment revealed a positive dynamic of the level of formation of the communicative competence of Bachelor's degree students.

Repeated measurements on the method of measuring the level of communicative competence of the student by Fahrutdinova, Fahrutdinov, & Konopatskaya (2014) made it possible to reveal the following results on the formation of the orientation value and communicative activity criteria: the first ten judgments: the lower than average level was noted in 10% of students, the average level in 22%, the higher than average level in 27% and the highest level in 41%.

The second group of judgments: the lower than average level was found in 4% of students, an average level of 17%, the higher than average level in 27% of respondents and the highest level in 52% of students.

Of the 136 respondents, 54% rated their level as high, putting themselves the highest score, 25% and 11% of the respondents rated their level of communication motivation by 4 and 3 points. Based on the data obtained, it is possible to say that the level is above average.

CONCLUSIONS

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research:

The concept of "development of the creative independence of undergraduate students in the context of introducing the credit technology of education" has been clarified and supplemented in terms of the advantages of this education system from the traditional one, namely: the use of innovative technologies to develop students' self-analyzing skills, which allows them to increase their creative activity and motivation to learn; determination by each student of an individual educational trajectory for the entire period of analysis; a change in the ratio of classroom and student independence in favor of the first, which allows the student to develop a creative approach for the analysis of disciplines and skills of research activities.

A technique for the development of creative independence in the process of forming the communicative competence of bachelor students, including conceptual (methodological characteristics), target (purpose and functions), procedural (methods, organizational forms of training, the system of exercise) and the resulting blocks that have been developed.

Pedagogical conditions for the development of the creative independence of Bachelor's degree students of higher education institutions have been revealed.

Features of credit technology and its implementation in Kazakhstan in the system of higher education were described:

the introduction of a credit system to assess the workload of students and teachers in following cases:

students' freedom to choose from the disciplines of choice, included in the working curriculum in the formation of an individual curriculum;

students' direct participation in the formation of their individual curriculum;

involvement of tutors in the educational process, who assist students in choosing an educational trajectory;

use of a score-rating system for evaluating academic achievements for each academic discipline;

providing the educational process with all necessary educational and methodological materials;

giving the students an opportunity to choose a professor in university.

Theoretical approaches to the development of the creative independence of bachelor students in the educational space of the university in foreign pedagogy, including Kazakhstan, have been revealed, which can be used to improve the Russian education system in the context of its integration into the global educational space in accordance with the Bologna process.

Practical significance of the research: materials of this research can be used by teachers of higher and secondary schools, further education system and retraining of teachers, supervisors in the development of educational and methodological tools to improve the efficiency of the learning process.

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